

ISic1243

Epitaph for Felicita, daughter of Hermodorus

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Largo di Chiesa di San Giovanni Gerosolimitano Di Malta

Coordinates

38.199072, 15.556499

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3548

Physical Description

A marble slab broken in two joining parts down the middle; minor damage /
loss to

the lower right corner

Dimensions

Height 29.5 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: 40 mm

Line 2: 31 mm

Line 3: 25 mm

Interlineation

not measured: mm

Text

1. Φηλικίτα
2. Ἑρμοδώρου
3. ἑτῶν ἕξ

Apparatus

Text based on I.Messina 31

Translation (en)

Felicita, daughter of Hermodorus, 6 years old

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492846

EDCS 38200022

PHI 140728

PHI 313663

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0416 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Bitto, I. 2001. *Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. Pelorias 7.* Messina. At 31

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5634

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1243. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353311>